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Waterfront Sustainable Open Solutions to Face Climate Change

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Abstract

The effects of climate change are increasing at an unprecedented rhythm, which demands adaptation and transformation of vulnerable waterfront territories. Cities aim to build up resilience, not only to mitigate losses, but also to transform themselves into stronger, improved built environments. Before the effective adaptation and mitigation, cities face years of discussions and/or lawsuits involving significant costs.

How can cities become more resilient? What must be transformed? Who should lead the process? When is the appropriate time to do it? To enhance resilience, it is necessary to recognize present gaps. Research, namely at geographical, historical, cultural, political, and climatic levels should contribute to develop approaches and find systematic means. There are effective new strategies that have emerged from bottom up initiatives. The protection of the urban environment and the enhancement of urban resilience come from interdisciplinary and comparative cases. The recent research that scratches innovative methodologies is increasingly relevant.

The scope of this research project is to develop a research network, associating architecture schools, urban research laboratories, local authorities and NGOs on architectural and urban design solutions to deal with the problem of the consequences of climate change on the waterfront. The network has the objective to research in different scales: 1) solutions for urban planning (the vast territory), 2) solutions for urban projects (in a scale of the district or smaller urban facade), 3) solutions for public spaces, 4) Architectural solutions at the building level, 5) The contribution of new technologies (warning devices or other) and 6) "social" solutions (organization of the affected populations).

Worldwide, there are many entities already working directly on the topic. This project values design processes that connect the traditional urban design method with multi-source urban big data and AI method

to evaluate the urban form, function, commercial activities, urban environment, ecology and human activity comprehensively.

The selection of best practices, include projects that succeed in conquering public support, integrating the signs of the collective identity based on the evaluation results. Climate change solutions can only be successful in ensuring a resilient city if they also engage citizens, educating them about challenges, solutions, and fostering possible changes in lifestyles. Each of these topics contributes to build component of existing solutions and a component on future or innovative solutions. The research will present the action from universities, research centers, local authorities, stakeholders and communities that are working together with high-density and ecological sensitive waterfront environments to make a link between master plan and future scenarios.

Keywords: waterfront, urban design, climate change, data & technology, innovative co-creation

Introduction

The challenge brought by climate change created by human's actions on the planet, raises multiple questions, opens new perspectives and consequently demands different responses. The discussion regards their impact, how to mitigate and improve the situation. The reduction of the impact of human actions includes the interest for new models.

Five European Cities are taken as laboratory of research, three sites in each city created fifteen possible answers within the Green Deals strategies. The declaration of the World Congress of the International Society of City and Regional Planners – ISOCARP organized in 2020 states a need for new solutions to look beyond the present climate conditions.

We advocate a territorial approach to climate action and resilience by promoting place-based policy responses

to accelerate efforts to mitigate climate change and to more effectively adapt to its local impacts. (...) This action will rely on systems level change and innovation such as in digitalization, big data, new global economic models, (...).¹ The statement is particularly meaningful on waterfront territories, while facing new patterns of natural disasters; they are particularly vulnerable in each of the five cities, Lisbon, Rome

Thessaloniki, Gdansk and Stockholm.

Carbon neutrality emerges as a common goal for the younger generation who claims the same rights and privileges as those of the previous generations. The growing importance of the topic is raising an exponential diversity of answers in order to mitigate and adapt waterfronts to climate change. Editor of the book *Enlightenment and Ecology*, Yavor Tarinski claims that:

"Climate change will deepen ongoing current crises. It has the potential to radically alter the face of the planet, making our future on it quite uncertain. In a sense it is a holistic crisis. Thus, the climate crisis has an existential character that places us on a crossroad – to continue down the road we are currently on, or choose a different path. That's why conventional approaches like responsible parliamentarism and green capitalism seems out of place and offer no real solution to climate change."²

An increasing number of authors agree that our industrialized world endangers, by its hyper consumption, the very future of humanity, thus our research includes the identification of communities that succeed to diminish our ecological footprint and place it as their first duty. The goal of "sos climate waterfront" research project is to find sustainable open solutions and disseminate them to larger audiences in five European Cities.

State of the Art

The reduction of biodiversity, unprecedented climate swings, and the raising costs of maintenance are symptoms of a planet struggling with illness. Human ecology is also something deeper than indispensable in order to further create the necessary relationship between human life and the law inscribed in nature itself. To enhance resilience of the built environment it requires a multidisciplinary approach. Along the lines of a wide range of authors discussing urban resilience, Ayda Eraydin defined a resilient system in terms of "its ability to absorb change and disturbance, and the persistence of systems while retaining its basic functions and structure".³ The persistence of systems raises important challenges for the next generations. To retain basic functions, it is necessary to mitigate risks and develop means to adapt.

The consciousness of the extractive impact of the consumed goods is complementary to the aim for health and positive behaviours. It necessarily leads to continuously consider life of the next generations.⁴

According to authors Vale and Campanella writing on resilient cities, finding a broader perspective will lead to understand the loss of resilience. They define resilience as "the ability to absorb change and disturbance" to the conditions of the community which in many cases is beyond climatic causes: Sometimes, social and political disasters are even self-inflicted, usually by regimes seeking drastic overhaul as a means to promote massive, rapid modernization.⁵

Climate change imposes transformation. Change itself is not necessarily the problem. There are many parameters to be considered, probably too many; therefore, it becomes hard to guess with certainty what the future could become. Transformation does not, by definition, compromise or promote resilience. It brings new challenges which can be converted into opportunities, according to Yoshiki Yamagata, Principal Researcher at the National Institute for Environmental Studies in Japan: Resilience is not a static state of a system. It is a process.

"The process of regeneration seeks to develop adaptation strategies and make waterfronts more resilient. A city is dynamic and is always changing. (...) Resilience is transformative, and in each transformation, tries to create a stronger, improved city".⁶

Some scientists claim that it is during the present decade that humanity will decide to balance the anthropogenic influence with natural habitats. Political decisions are required to take affirmative actions and measures that are effective regarding public health. During the pandemic lockdown, political leaders and local communities have shown the capacity of nations to collaborate and react to protect humans. The quality of life of people, their harmony with the environment, the engagement of natural systems, the promotion of local ecologies and mutual help between nature and human presence.

Hope in technical solutions, merely technical, risk to take into consideration symptoms that do not correspond to the most profound problems. It is necessary to interpret the behaviours of people and each culture; understanding the development of a social group supposes a historical process, within a cultural context, that constantly requires the role of local social authors, from their own perspective. All research that was carried out has been to "cultivate curiosity without being obsessed by utility or profit. In fact, the fundamental discoveries that have revolutionized the history of humankind are the result, mostly, of research far removed from any utilitarian

objective.”⁷

Procedures of justice and scientific information are needed to be considered in order to relate all of the available parameters. Most of the parameters are increasingly difficult to guess with certainty, though the correct combination of parameters is useful into predicting and ascertaining what the future could become.

New paths

In this moment of crisis and conflicting perspectives it is particularly relevant to observe the actions and the positions of the younger generations concerned with the discussion. There are several main complementary ingredients to be considered: nature regeneration in the urban environment, resilience to extreme climate variations, renewable energy production, rainwater collection for reuse, reduction of CO₂ emissions from people’s transport, building energy consumption and construction materials.

Younger researchers were encouraged to integrate scientific high-tech solutions with holistic sustainable strategies and share a critical perspective on economic activities spread worldwide that follow models of continuous growth. It is appropriate to observe their growing awareness and understand how human presence might be less damaging for the planet. What can be improved to mitigate ecological disasters, the exponential loss of biodiversity or how it might be possible to reach a healthy balance of CO₂ emissions?

In each site, there are a number of measures to be incorporated. The work carried out includes an interdisciplinary research⁸ between experts, researchers, professional doctoral students, and the involvement of local institutions that will inevitably have an impact on future decisions. In short the research group privilege design solutions that implement a symbiotic approach by promoting the sponge effect. One that is able to absorb extreme swings of temperature and water. The sponge is resilient, not static. It cooperates in the process of transformation while sustaining permanence. From their perspective, promoting a smooth dialogue between the natural and the built environment is able to regenerate nature.

Conservative political leaders and CEOs of large corporations such as Microsoft⁹, along with other opinion makers, believe scientific innovative solutions and high technology will provide the necessary answers for the climatic crisis. In the five European cities the research is seeking for solutions that improve their resilience, like sponges that are able to absorb without being degraded. The effect of a sponge is smooth, the water is soaked up

discreetly, and the temperature dissipates and gradually returns to its initial condition. The concept of a sponge applied to the built environment requires a shift in the way urban waterfronts have been designed until recently. Sponges take and give, they are passive and active, and open a new realm of opportunities for contemporary design.

The strategies reinforced in the last twenty years give us the evidence of how it can play a role model on waterfront community’s capacity to adapt to climate change.¹⁰ To contribute to the present debate each parameter should be addressed independently but there is an urgent need to find new paradigms as Canadian philosopher Harvey Mead¹¹ states:

“We have no choice: either we change our system by a massive community effort, or this system will collapse under the weight of its excesses, whether of an economic, social or ecological nature.”

Methodology

The strategy applied to each of the fifteen sites makes use of historic and geographic records. The collection of data is used to construct patterns of development, feed algorithms and integrate the support of artificial intelligence to design future possible scenarios.

During the 30 days workshop, a group of international and multidisciplinary researchers have access to the present debate and the recent discussions.¹² They work in groups of four or five persons; they are encouraged to invest in the potential inventiveness of future solutions based on the local cultural context.¹³ At the end of the workshop, each group seek for strategies supported on scientific rigorous use of data and ecologic sensibility to produce imaginative green/blue solutions.

The European Green Deal has a strong influence among researchers, initially, some sought to copy solutions applied elsewhere. It soon became evident that there are no blueprints, and each city has to invent its own solution. The challenges presented by the anthropogenic action on climate change demand the search for innovation, and solutions that are not repeatable, that require the interpretation of each place and the imagination of a specific design.

The central question shared by researchers, expresses the general perception of the next younger generation. Previous models seem outdated and the urgency to find adequate answers is brought to the centre of the discussion. Promoting solutions of circular economy, the European Green Deal takes over in search for new potential models, which introduces the transition to the core of the debate. In his book *Political Ecology: Beyond Environmentalism*, Dimitrios Roussopoulos stated that

there are fundamental questions to be addressed:

"Despite many international meetings, dealing with every subject from biodiversity to climate change, the national political elites have found it impossible to come to meaningful agreements to deal with the environmental crisis. [...] There is no avoiding of imagining new and different scenarios than the status quo. Surely another world is possible."¹⁴

The methodology adopted brought local knowledge, and local talent to find the best local solutions from local designers. Several authors claim the importance of linking existing public spaces and waterside areas, as argued by Nyka & Burda, referring to social benefits, and advantages of building a more comprehensive and creative city landscape, though the means to implement these measures can be interpreted broadly.¹⁵

Solutions intended to combine a good balance between rigor and creativity, while speculating on and opening up new perspectives. Invention relies on both, and flourishes when they are in balance. The central question regards the inevitable process of regeneration. Where should "sponge" strategies be implemented? How may adaption and mitigation improve the resilience of waterfronts?

Outcomes

To shrink the ecological footprint and improve resilience the implementation of long-term strategies is required. Research from international and multidisciplinary backgrounds are committed to the exchange of best practices and further stimulate new ideas that are occasionally useful in finding solutions that are betting in the future or in other words present the best guessing to face the present threats.¹⁶

To envision the new opportunities, it is necessary to engage the next generation, namely graduate students and young professionals that contribute positively to the discussion. Planning regulations, academic perception of planning and their methods are outdated. The methodology adopted in the workshop aims to develop concepts useful for the future. Young researcher's contributions may be shaped in a creative and intense way, with new strengths that show a commitment to future generations, or it may be seen as a source of despair of irreversible mistakes towards a dead end.¹⁷

Researchers were encouraged to think "out of the box" to imagine beyond predictable scenarios and to take risks. The concepts of symbiosis and biophilia in urban ecology are transversally integrated and applied in the design to develop solutions that may become an inspiration to new visions.

The research, by design, takes into consideration the influence of geographic conditions, historical buildings,

and climatic indicators. The frequency of extreme events affects the urban environment with floods and high tides, tropical hurricanes, droughts, and the urban heat island effect. The expenses that each of the events bring to the municipalities, stakeholders and the community require the improvement of related infrastructures and consequently exponential cost.

Historical heritage, industrial artefacts, buildings, docks, cranes, and canals are relevant, each have address climatic conditions that are useful when designing future systems of circular economy, to build a post-industrial area that is committed to capturing CO2 that mix ecologic solution of passive energy, vertical farms, and floating platforms and innovative systems to protect biodiversity and human presence in the territory.

Data related to sea level rise and frequent floods influenced the researchers to redefine the contour of the line separating the land and water. Geographic data proves the necessity for new infrastructures, the use of renewable energy sources, combined with green systems and urban farming and the protection of local biodiversity in land and on the water. Together, these measures empower sustainability goals.

European Processes

The illustration of the hypothesis presented for each location in developing solutions and strategies to face climate change is innovative. A high level of expertise and international excellency among professionals integrates our research project, thus providing the competences necessary to develop futuristic solutions for waterfronts. Researchers from several European countries have analyzed geographic and historic records, data collected in the last 100 years in Lisbon, Gdansk, Thessaloniki, Rome and Stockholm. In each city, researchers processed large quantities of information on climate, pollution, energy consumption, transformation of the built environment and consumption behaviours.

Sustaining new approaches requires a systematic and rigorous collection of data, the identification of patterns of evolution.

To elaborate future scenarios, it is necessary to combine rigor and invention. It is mandatory to establish an open dialogue with local representatives before imagining future scenarios for adapting and mitigating risks for specific sites. Rigorous approaches do not tend to value innovative visions. Innovation presents new ideas or methods to be tested for the first time and does not strictly emerge from being accurate. The question is how to find the right balance between the two, imagination and accuracy?

During the processes there is the enhancement of

critical thinking and scepticism. Take for granted that only a tiny portion of the results will be valuable. Most of the outcomes of an experimental workshop are not useful, they are wasted, but the small part that is relevant is worth the effort and opens new perspectives.

The speculative design proposals produced during the meetings are becoming relevant due to their capacity to combine systems that were not necessarily related. The integration and the connection of them offer the opportunity to envision integrated mechanisms in symbiosis. Among the participants, the imminent and inevitable climatic disaster is not taken from a pessimistic perspective only. The new climatic patterns also sustain new ideas and become a creative engine to redefine the rules, the goals and most importantly, the dream of the next generation.

In short, the design proposals briefly presented in this paper prioritize the following aims: integrity of the city and the protection of the urban environment as a place of integration, unity, safety, and sense of belonging. They succeed in contributing to the present discussion by combining systems that are not related.

The participants acknowledged that possibility when processing the scientific data; they did not ignore the facts, though they did decide to invest in an optimistic vision based on the perception that previous generations have been able to move quickly and respond positively.

The engagement of young professionals from different disciplines with graduate students from all over Europe is particularly useful for the discussion. The previous generations did not anticipate that modernity and strategies of control of nature would lead humanity to the present situation. Participants involved in the meetings do not see it as a source of despair of irreversible mistakes towards a dead end. On the contrary difficulties become an engine of innovative design, include smart solutions and new governance shaped in a creative and intense way, with new strengths that show a commitment to the future generations.

Conclusion

To face the climatic crisis there is no single solution, the solution arises from a multiplicity of factors and their correct relation.

Each site faces different challenges and raise complementary questions regarding the communities, local infrastructures, and the local ecology. Human settlements located in low lying coastal areas or near streams, rivers, or the seacoast likely have a higher risk of damage from sea level rise or flooding.¹⁸

The illustration of the hypothesis presented for each location in developing solutions and strategies to face

climate change is a meaningful contribution with cultural impact on stakeholder's municipality representatives and the community. Researchers from several European countries analyzing geographic and historic records, data collected in the last 100 years and processing large quantities of information on climate, pollution, energy consumption, transformation of the built environment are able to contribute with innovative solutions, imagining future scenarios for adapting and mitigating risks for each site.

The methodology and defined outputs are possible to use outside Europe by sharing the state of the art and using similar new paths. Image 5 shows a summary of principles and the urban/architecture design selected from a Graduate Architecture Studio carried on at Université Laval under my supervision. Other researchers from Laval in Canada also have been published in our H2020 research publications enhancing scientific collaboration across the Atlantic.

The expansion of the consumerism society to larger numbers of the world population leads ecosystems to unprecedented levels of stress and destruction. Such evidence is so hard to face that a large number of humans develop a sense of denial and keep their current lifestyles. It is the way human beings organize themselves to feed all self-destructive addictions: trying not to see them, struggling not to recognize them, postponing important decisions, acting as if humanity could go on.

A central aspect of consumerism society is the continuous growth of consumption of resources and energy. Several experts agree on the need to prioritize green buildings and urban transport. But it is difficult for some measures deemed necessary to be peacefully taken by society without a substantial improvement in transport, enhancing frequency of services and security. In the five waterfront cities the importance of these points of view always contributes to the analysis of the built environment. The projects and solutions presented in this book were not driven by the pursuit of beauty. This has been considered to not be enough, because it must serve another kind of beauty.

To deal with the complexity of the ecological crisis and its multiple causes, there is a growing recognition it cannot come from a single way of interpreting and transforming reality. It is an opportunity to address the diversity of cultural conditions, learn the art and poetry, the inner life and spirituality of each community. It becomes evident that to build ecology, and the reparation of all that has been destroyed, no branch of science and no form of wisdom can be neglected.

Endnotes

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Figure 1. Water-pumping system from al-Jazzari, The book of knowledge of ingenious mechanical devices (1206)

ARCHITECTURAL SOLUTIONS

A space to accommodate water

Figure 2. Architecture Solutions A space to accommodate water, SOS Climate Waterfront, Rome book

Figure 3. SOS Climate Waterfront, Lisbon Book

Figure 4. Human impacts on water

Figure 5. Green Deal Architectural Solutions, by Raphaëlle Gosselin Supervised by Pedro Ressano Garcia